

Synthesis, molecular and crystalline architecture of a tetracoordinated dinuclear mercury(II) iodide complex containing a bis(didentate) congregator[†]

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Abstract : A tetracoordinated dinuclear mercury(II) iodide complex of the type $[\text{Hg}_2(\text{L})\text{I}_4]$ (**1**) [$\text{L} = \text{N,N}'\text{-(bis(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,6-hexanediamine}$] has been prepared and characterized using microanalytical, spectroscopic, thermal and X-ray crystallographic results. Structural analysis reveals that the classical tetradentate Schiff base (**L**) encapsulate two metal centers in *bis(didentate) congregation* mode. Each mercury(II) center in **1** is in a distorted tetrahedral coordination environment with HgN_2I_2 chromophore. Hg(1) is attached with two N atoms of **L** and two terminal iodides, whereas neighbouring Hg(2) is ligated to the similar rest N donor set of the same Schiff base completing its *bis(didentate)* mode along with two terminal iodides. In solid-state, dinuclear units of **1** pack through cooperative intermolecular C-H...I hydrogen bond, and $\pi\cdots\pi$ and halogen... π interactions giving rise to a 2D sheet structure. In DMF solutions at room temperature **L** displays high-energy intraligand $^1(\pi\text{-}\pi^*)$ fluorescence, but this fluorescence intensity is quenched in **1** due to the heavy metal ion effect.

Keywords : Dinuclear mercury(II), Schiff base congregator, terminal iodide, X-ray structure, fluorescence.

Introduction

Design and synthesis^{1,2} of mono-, di- and polynuclear coordination compounds of mercury(II)³⁻⁷ continues unabated for the preparation of different functional materials⁸⁻¹¹ coupled with interesting electronic and optoelectronic properties^{11,12-14}. Self-assembly¹⁵ using preassigned molar ratios of the metal ion, different organic spacers and suitable bridging units give rise to different coordination molecules and supramolecular entities with tunable properties. Utilizing the veracities of coordination geometries around this $5d^{10}$ ion, diverse molecular and crystalline architectures^{16,17} of different shapes and sizes¹⁸ may be accessed through strong metal-ligand covalent bonds¹⁹ and multiple weak non-covalent forces²⁰⁻²². Schiff bases^{23,24} are widely used as chelator as well as congregator affording different functional materials with interesting molecular aggregates and crystalline architectures. Iodide^{25,26} is a suitable terminal/bridging unit which in combination with organic ligands gives rise to different

structures through its different coordination modes. Recently, we have reported^{27,28} some bivalent mercury complexes in combination with polyamines and Schiff bases of different denticities. In the present work, a tetradentate Schiff base, N,N'-(bis(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,6-hexanediamine (**L**) has been chosen (Scheme 1) to isolate mercury(II) compounds with different geometries and molecular properties. Successfully, one tetracoordinated dinuclear mercury(II) iodide compound, $[\text{Hg}_2(\text{L})\text{I}_4]$ (**1**) is synthesized and X-ray crystallographically characterized. The synthesis, structure and spectroscopic behavior of this new compound is described below.

Scheme 1

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

One-pot synthesis of the building components like HgI_2 and Schiff base (L) in appropriate molar ratio (2 : 1) in methanol-dimethylformamide solvent mixture at room temperature affords a tetracoordinated dinuclear mercury(II) complex of the type $[\text{Hg}_2(\text{L})\text{I}_4]$ (**1**). The reaction is reproducible, as is evident from repetitive microanalytical and spectral results. The reproducibility reflects an inherent tendency towards the formation of **1**. The main synthetic reaction is summarized in eq. (1) :

The new complex **1** was characterized using microanalytical (C, H and N), spectroscopic, thermal and other physicochemical results. The microanalytical data are in good conformity with the formulation **1**. The air-stable and moisture-insensitive compound **1** is insoluble in methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane and acetonitrile but moderately soluble in warm dimethylformamide. In DMF solution **1** behaves non-electrolyte as reflected from its low conductivity value ($\sim 5 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)²⁹.

Spectroscopic studies :

In IR spectrum of **1**, the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ plus $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ stretching vibrations³⁰ at ~ 1640 and $\sim 1590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed due to metal bound Schiff base. Weak bands in the range $2937\text{--}2853 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assignable to the aliphatic C-H stretching frequency³⁰. All other characteristic organic ligand vibrations are seen in the range $1600\text{--}600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The electronic spectrum of the complex **1** in DMF solution exhibits strong absorptions at $\sim 272 \text{ nm}$, presumably due to ligand-based $n\text{-}\pi^*/\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition³¹.

Luminescence properties :

In DMF solutions at room temperature the photoluminescence behaviours of free ligand (L) and its compound **1** were recorded. These are depicted in Fig. 1. Upon photoexcitation at the corresponding absorption bands in DMF solutions free ligand exhibits broad fluorescent emission centered at 470 nm (for L) whereas the corresponding mercury(II) complex **1** shows no fluorescence bands. This quenching of fluorescence intensity value in this complex as compared to that of free ligand (L) may presumably be due to the heavy metal ion effect^{33,34} on the ligand upon coordination.

Fig. 1. Fluorescence behaviours of L and **1** in DMF solutions at 298 K.

Thermal properties :

To examine thermal stability of **1** thermogravimetric analysis (TG) was made between 30 and $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a static atmosphere of nitrogen. The TG curve (Fig. 2) of **1** indicates that it is stable up to $174 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at which temperature decomposition commences and decomposes completely in the temperature range $174\text{--}538 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with no residual part remaining after total decomposition (calcd. : $\text{L} + 4 \text{ I} + 2 \text{ HgO} = 102.36\%$; obsd. : 102.95%). This may be due to the evaporation of the final residue (probably HgO) at higher temperature. The result shows that the compound has reasonable thermal stability in the above temperature range.

Molecular and crystal structure of $[\text{Hg}_2(\text{L})\text{I}_4]$ (**1**) :

In order to define the coordination spheres conclusively, single-crystal X-ray diffraction measurement of **1** was made. An ORTEP representation of the individual unit and perspective view of the packing diagram for **1** are shown in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. Selected bond distances and angles relevant to the coordination spheres of **1** are represented in Table 1 and non-covalent interaction parameters for the complex **1** are given in Table 2.

Structural analysis of $[\text{Hg}_2(\text{L})\text{I}_4]$ (**1**) reveals that classical tetradentate Schiff base (L) encapsulates two metal centers in *bis(didentate) congregation* fashion. Each mercury(II) center adopts a distorted tetrahedral geometry with an HgN_2I_2 chromophore. $\text{Hg}(1)$ is surrounded by two terminal iodide [I(1) and I(2)] and two N atoms [N(1) and N(2)] of the Schiff base (L), whereas the

Fig. 2. Thermal behaviour of **1**.

Fig. 3. An ORTEP diagram of **1** with atom numbering scheme.

Fig. 4. 2D sheet structure in **1** formed through cooperative intermolecular C-H...I hydrogen bond, and π ... π and halogen... π interactions along crystallographic *bc* plane.

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å), bond angles (°) for **1**

Bond distances			
Hg1-I1	2.6754(7)	Hg2-I3	2.6881(6)
Hg1-I2	2.6627(7)	Hg2-I4	2.7044(6)
Hg1-N1	2.398(6)	Hg2-N1A	2.396(6)
Hg1-N2	2.386(6)	Hg2-N2A	2.430(6)
Bond angles			
N1-Hg1-I1	114.63(15)	N1A-Hg2-I3	110.33(14)
N1-Hg1-I2	109.53(15)	N1A-Hg2-I4	123.83(14)
N1-Hg1-N2	69.83(19)	N1A-Hg2-N2A	68.7(2)
N2-Hg1-I1	104.26(14)	N2A-Hg2-I3	114.17(15)
N2-Hg1-I2	119.63(14)	N2A-Hg2-I4	95.91(14)
I1-Hg1-I2	125.80(2)	I3-Hg2-I4	124.73(2)

Table 2. Non-covalent force parameters for **1**

Hydrogen bond and halogen... π interaction parameters (Å, °)				
D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A
C1A-H1A...I4 ^a	0.9300	3.0000	3.788(8)	144.00
Hg1-I2...Cg(4) ^b	2.6627(7)	3.832(3)	6.363(3)	156.54(5)
π ... π interactions (Å, °)				
Ring-Ring	Cg-Cg distance	Dihedral angle (i, j)	Perpendicular distances between baricenters (i, j)	Slippage
Cg(4)...Cg(4) ^c	3.739(5)	0.00	3.688(3)	0.609
Symmetry code : (a) 1-x,2-y,1-z; (b) x,y,z; (c) 2-x,2-y,1-z.				
Cg(4) : N(1A)→C(1A)→C(2A)→C(3A)→C(4A)→C(5A).				

neighbouring Hg(2) is ligated to the similar rest N donor set [N(1A) and N(2A)] of the same ligand (L), completing its bis(didentate) mode and two terminal iodide [I(3) and I(4)]. The intramolecular Hg...Hg distance is 6.532 Å. Distortion from ideal tetrahedral geometry is due to asymmetric nature of the Schiff base and deviations of the refine angles (109.5°). Hg-N(Schiff base) distances lie within a range of 2.386(6)–2.430(6) Å whereas the range of Hg-I distances is 2.6627(7)–2.7044(6) Å.

The dinuclear units of **1** self-assemble through cooperative intermolecular C-H...I hydrogen bond, and π ... π and halogen... π interactions (Table 2) giving rise to a 2D supramolecular sheet structure along crystallographic *bc* plane (Fig. 4). Two dinuclear units assemble through intermolecular weak C-H...I hydrogen bond to form a tetrameric unit. The terminal iodine atom (I4) is hydrogen bond acceptor whereas one C-H (H1A) of aromatic pyridine ring is the donor (C1A-H1A...I4^a: 3.000 Å, 144.00°; ^asymmetry code : 1-x,2-y,1-z). Face-to-face π ... π [ring(4)-

Table 3. Crystallographic data and structure refinement in **1**

Compound	1
CCDC No.	1415352
Chemical formula	C ₃₀ H ₃₀ N ₄ I ₄ Hg ₂
Formula mass	1355.36
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1
<i>a</i> (Å)	9.0988(3)
<i>b</i> (Å)	13.1249(4)
<i>c</i> (Å)	16.0014(5)
α (°)	104.9860(18)
β (°)	98.1690(16)
γ (°)	96.2780(17)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1805.72(10)
λ (Å)	0.71073
ρ_{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	2.493
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>T</i> (K)	296
μ (mm ⁻¹)	11.928
<i>F</i> (000)	1148
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.12 × 0.12 × 0.10
θ ranges (°)	2.85 to 28.31
<i>h/k/l</i>	-12,12/-17,17/-21,21
Reflections collected	33902
Independent reflections	8923
Data/restraints/parameters	8923/0/361
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.054
Final <i>R</i> 1 values [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.0356
Final w <i>R</i> (<i>F</i> ²) values [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.0881
Final <i>R</i> 1 values (all data)	0.0653
Final w <i>R</i> (<i>F</i> ²) values (all data)	0.1175
Goodness of fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.033
Largest peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	0.94 and -1.51
$R = \frac{\sum F_o - F_c }{\sum F_o }$, $wR = \frac{[\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \sum w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}}{[\sum w(F_o^2) + (0.0578P)^2]^{1/2}}$, $w = 1 / [\sum^2 (F_o^2) + (0.0578P)^2]$ where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2) / 3$.	

ring(4) : Cg(4)...Cg(4)^c distance 3.739(5) Å; vertical displacement of Cg(4) : 3.688(3) and slippage : 0.609 Å; Cg(4) = N(1A)→C(1A)→C(2A)→C(3A)→C(4A)→C(5A); ^csymmetry code : 2-x,2-y,1-z] and halogen... π [Hg1-I2...Cg(4)^b: 3.832(3) Å, 156.54(5)°; ^bsymmetry code : x,y,z] interactions stabilize these tetrameric units resulting to a 2D supramolecular sheet structure along crystallographic *bc* plane.

Conclusion

One neutral dinuclear mercury(II) iodide complex in combination with one bis(didentate) congregator (L) is

isolated and X-ray crystallographically characterized. The compound affords an aesthetically pleasant crystalline architecture through multiple weak non-covalent forces. This work on such compound illustrates a potentially versatile approach towards isolation of uncharged metal-organic frameworks.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity 2-benzoylpyridine (Lancaster, UK), 1,6-hexanediamine (Lancaster, India) and mercury(II) iodide (E. Merck, India) were purchased from respective concerns and used as received. All other chemicals and solvents were AR grade and used as received. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air.

Caution! Mercury and its compounds are toxic³⁵. Only a small amount of these materials should be prepared and handled with care.

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–400 cm⁻¹) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. Thermal studies were made with a Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DTA analyzer heated from 30–800 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. Ground state absorptions were measured with a Jasco model V-530 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Fluorescence measurements were done using a Hitachi Fluorescence Spectrofluorimeter F-4500.

Synthesis of Schiff base (L) :

2-Benzoylpyridine (0.732 g, 4 mmol) was refluxed with 1,6-hexanediamine (0.232 g, 2 mmol) in dehydrated alcohol (25 cm³). After 10 h the reaction solution was evaporated under reduced pressure to yield a gummy mass, which was dried and stored *in vacuo* over CaCl₂ for subsequent use. Yield : 0.716 g (80%). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₀H₃₀N₄ (L) : C, 80.68; H, 6.77; N, 12.55. Found : C, 80.84; H, 6.88; N, 12.67%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν(C=N) 1590; UV-Vis (λ, nm) : 266, 280.

Synthesis of complex [Hg₂(L)₄] (1) :

L (0.447 g, 1 mmol) in MeOH-DMF (9 : 1) mixture (20 cm³) was added dropwise to a HgI₂ (0.908 g, 2 mmol) solution in methanol (10 cm³). After filtration through a fine glass frit, the supernatant yellowish-brown solution was kept in air for slow evaporation. Yellowish-brown crystals of **1** that deposited within a couple of days, were collected by filtration and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield : 0.813 g (60%). Anal. Calcd. for

C₃₀H₃₀N₄I₄Hg₂ (**1**) : C, 26.58; H, 2.23; N, 4.13. Found : C, 26.42; H, 2.18; N, 4.26%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : ν(C-H) 2937, 2853; ν(C=N) 1640; ν(C=C) 1590; UV-Vis (λ, nm) : 272.

X-Ray crystallographic analysis :

Diffraction data of the single crystal of **1** were collected at 296 K on a Bruker SMART APEX II CCD area-detector diffractometer using graphite monochromated Mo-Kα radiation (0.71073 Å). The detector frames were integrated by use of the program SAINT³⁶ and absorption correction was performed with SADABS³⁷. The structure was solved by direct methods, using the SHELXTL³⁸ program. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters. The H atoms were placed in calculated positions after checking their positions in the difference map. All calculations were carried out using SHELXL-2013³⁹, SHELXTL, PLATON⁴⁰, ORTEP-32⁴¹ and Mercury 3.3⁴² programs. A summary of the crystallographic data and structure determination parameter for this complex is given in Table 3.

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center (CCDC No. 1415352 for **1**). Copy of this information can be obtained free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

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